

Epstein Bar virus is the cause of systemic lupus erythematosus

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Abstract

Objective. Several studies provided some evidence that Epstein Barr virus (EBV) might play a role in the pathogenesis of systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE). Still, there are conflicting reports too. To determine whether EBV is causally related to SLE a systematic review of available case control studies was performed.

Methods. This systematic review and meta-analysis should answer among other questions the following: is there a cause effect relationship between EBV and SLE? The method of the *conditio sine qua non* relationship was used to proof the hypothesis *without EBV infection no SLE*. The mathematical formula of the causal relationship *k* was used to proof the hypothesis whether there is a cause effect relationship between Epstein-Barr virus and systemic lupus erythematosus. Significance was indicated by a p-value of less than 0.05.

Results. The studies analyzed were able to provide convincing evidence that Epstein-Barr virus is a necessary condition (a *conditio sine qua non*) of systemic lupus erythematosus. Furthermore, the studies analyzed provide impressive evidence of a cause-effect relationship between Epstein-Barr virus and systemic lupus erythematosus.

Conclusion. EBV infection is necessary condition of systemic lupus erythematosus and much more than this. Epstein-Barr virus is the cause of systemic lupus erythematosus.

Keywords: *Epstein-Bar virus, systemic lupus erythematosus, causal relationship.*

1. Introduction

The Systemic lupus erythematosus is a very complex autoimmune systemic diseases without a definite pathogenesis. SLE is characterized by the presence of multiple autoantibodies (Olsen & Karp, 2014), an impaired cell-mediated immunity, an altered T cell function (Labonte et al., 2018) and by polyclonal B cell activation which may effect

almost any organ system. There are worldwide differences in the prevalence (Rees, Doherty, Grainge, Lanyon, & Zhang, 2017) of SLE. In North America about 241/100 000 people suffer from SLE. The term lupus was coined by *Hebernus of Tours* in his *Miracles of St. Martin* in the tenth century (Gordon & Isenberg, 2016). In 1869/1872, the Hungarian born dermatologist *Moriz Kaposi* was the first to describe the systemic nature of lupus in detail (Kaposi, 1872). *Hargraves* et al. described LE cells in 1948 (Hargraves, Richmond, & Morton, 1948). The first trials towards an understanding of the pathogenesis of lupus were published by Morteo (Morteo, Franklin, McEwen, Phythyon, & Tanner, 1961), Helyer and Howie (Helyer & Howie, 1963) and Leonhardt (Leonhardt, 1964). Diagnostic criteria for systemic lupus erythematosus were first proposed in 1971 by the American College of Rheumatology (A. S. Cohen, Reynolds, & Franklin, 1971). Philip Showalter Hench (1896–1965), awarded with the 1950 Nobel Prize for Medicine and Physiology, the founding father of glucocorticoid treatment of rheumatoid arthritis (Hench, Kendall, Slocumb, & Polley, 1949), was first to suppress some features of SLE by glucocorticoids in 1950. Steinberg et al. conducted the first randomized clinical trial to treat SLE with cyclophosphamide (Steinberg et al., 1971) in 1971. Epstein-Barr virus infects a majority of individuals worldwide and generates multiple antibodies (Olsen & Karp, 2014) in the serum. It is believed that especially Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) contributes to development of SLE. Evans et al. (Evans, Rothfield, & Niederman, 1971) found in 1971 raised antibody titers to Epstein-Barr virus in systemic lupus erythematosus patients. James et al. (James et al., 1997) found Epstein-Barr viral DNA in peripheral blood lymphocytes of all 32 of the lupus patients but only 23 of the 32 matched controls. Finally, the review and meta-analysis of Hanlon et al. (Hanlon, Avenell, Aucott, & Vickers, 2014) and of Li et al. (Li, Zeng, Wu, & Zhou, 2019) provided some evidence of an association between EBV infection and SLE. However, the previous systematic reviews and meta-analysis have failed to establish Epstein-Barr virus as the cause or a cause of systemic lupus erythematosus. The nature of the relationship between an Epstein-Barr Virus infection and SLE, in particular the question of causality, remains to be fully elucidated.

2. Material and Methods

Epstein-Barr Virus (Epstein, Achong, & Barr, 1964) is a herpes virus determined by a large double-stranded DNA genome which itself is enclosed with an icosahedral capsid, including viral capsid antigen (VCA). EBV is able to infect B cells and to establish a latent cycle while persisting for life within the long-lived human memory B-cell

population (Niller, Wolf, & Minarovits, 2008). EBV possesses several immunomodulatory properties (Kanegane, Wakiguchi, Kanegane, Kurashige, & Tosato, 1997), an EBV replication is associated with expression of some lytic cycle genes (Toussirof & Roudier, 2007), including VCA and early antigen (EA). The detection of EBV antibodies specific for EBV viral antigens is indicative of EBV infection (IgM, EA) or EBV reactivation.

2.1. Material

2.1.1. Search Strategy

For the questions addressed in this paper, the database PubMed was searched for serologically based studies conducted in any country which investigated the relationship between EBV and SLE by EBV antibodies. Those articles were formally considered for a review which provided access to data without a significant data access barrier.

The Data of the Studies Analyzed

1. Identification of records	Size	Total
Records identified by searching in the databases		
PubMed	438	
Google Scholar	0	
Web of Science	0	
Additional records identified from other sources	2	440
2. Clean-up of search (Screening)		
Records removed after verifying duplication	0	
Records excluded by title	411	
Records excluded due to other reasons (Articles outside the inclusion criteria)	2	
3. Eligibility		
Articles evaluated for eligibility	27	
Articles excluded for various reasons		
- Data were self-contradictory (Table 2)	11	
- Data access barriers	0	
4. Included		
Articles included in the meta-analysis (Table 1)		16

Table 1.

Flow Diagram of the article selection process. Adopted from PRISMA 2009 (Moher, Liberati, Tetzlaff, & Altman, 2009).

2.1.2. Studies considered for re-analysis

The studies of Yokochi et al. (Yokochi, Yanagawa, Kimura, & Mizushima, 1989), Marchini et al. (Marchini, Dolcher, Sabbatini, Klein, & Migliorini, 1994), Tsai et al. (Tsai, Chiang, Kao, & Hsieh, 1995), James (1997) et al. (James et al., 1997), Westgeest et al. (Westgeest, van Loon, van der Logt, van de Putte, & Boerbooms, 1989), Kitagawa et al. (Kitagawa, Iho, Yokochi, & Hoshino, 1988), Lau et al. (Lau, Yuen, Chan, & Wong, 1998), Stratta et al. (Stratta et al., 1999), James (2001) et al. (James et al., 2001), Chen et al. (C.-J. Chen et al., 2005), Parks et al. (Parks et al., 2005), Berkun et al.

(Berkun et al., 2009), Chen et al. (D.-Y. Chen et al., 2010), Draborg et al. (A. H. Draborg et al., 2012), Csuka et al. (Csuka et al., 2013), Han et al. (Han et al., 2018), were not self-contradictory (**Table 2**) and were considered for meta-analysis.

Table 2. Studies considered for a reanalysis

Study ID	Year	N	Case_P	Case_T	Con_P	Con_T	Odds Ratio	OR 95 % CI lower	OR upper	p(SINE)	X ² (SINE)	p Value (SINE)	k	IOU
Yokochi et al.	1989	25	9	11	2	14	27,00	3,17	229,97	0,92000	0,3636363636	0,5465	0,6753	-0,1200
Marchini et al.	1994	60	34	40	15	20	1,89	0,50	7,17	0,90000	0,9000000000	0,3428	0,1218	0,4833
Tsai et al.	1995	36	13	16	15	20	1,44	0,29	7,25	0,91667	0,5625000000	0,4533	0,0747	0,2222
James et al.	1997	270	116	117	107	153	49,87	6,76	367,95	0,99630	0,0085470085	0,9263	0,3817	0,2593
Westgeest et al.	1998	98	10	14	56	84	1,25	0,36	4,34	0,95918	1,1428571429	0,2850	0,0355	-0,1837
Kitagawa et al.	1998	131	64	65	52	66	17,23	2,19	135,40	0,99237	0,0153846154	0,9013	0,3089	0,3817
Lau et al.	1998	56	27	34	4	22	17,36	4,43	68,01	0,87500	1,4411764706	0,2299	0,6015	0,1607
Strata et al.	1999	115	55	60	33	55	7,33	2,53	21,22	0,95652	0,4166666667	0,5186	0,3732	0,2870
James et al.	2001	588	195	196	370	392	11,59	1,55	86,67	0,99830	0,0051020408	0,9431	0,1241	0,2942
Chen et al.	2005	72	31	36	30	36	1,24	0,34	4,50	0,93056	0,6944444444	0,4047	0,0386	0,3472
Parks et al.	2005	506	220	230	256	276	1,72	0,79	3,75	0,98024	0,4347826087	0,5097	0,0611	0,3953
Berkun et al.	2009	260	114	120	127	140	1,94	0,72	5,29	0,97692	0,3000000000	0,5839	0,0821	0,3885
Chen et al.	2010	464	81	94	308	370	1,25	0,66	2,39	0,97198	1,7978723404	0,1800	0,0320	0,0409
Draborg et al.	2012	80	48	60	15	20	1,33	0,40	4,40	0,85000	2,4000000000	0,1213	0,0529	0,5375
Csuka et al.	2012	646	286	301	310	345	2,15	1,15	4,03	0,97678	0,7475083056	0,3873	0,0964	0,3885
Han et al.	2018	192	104	116	68	76	1,02	0,40	2,62	0,93750	1,2413793103	0,2652	0,0029	0,5000
Total		3599	1407	1510	1768	2089								+0,274

Alpha = 0,05

Degrees of freedom = 16

X² CRITICAL (SINE) = 26,296

X² Calculated (SINE) = 12,47

2.1.2. Studies not considered for re-analysis

The studies of Ngou et al. 1996 (Ngou & Segondy, 1996), Zhang et al. 1999 (Zhang, Li, Liu, & Jiang, 1999), Huggins et al. 2005 (Huggins, Todd, & Powell, 2005), Tazi et al. 2009 (Tazi, Fehri, Elghrari, Ouazzani, & Benchemsi, 2009), US et al. 2011 (Us, Cetin, Ka ifo lu, Ka ifo lu, & Akgün, 2011), Essen et al. 2012 (Esen et al., 2012), Broccolo et al. 2013 (Broccolo et al., 2013), Draborg et al. 2014 (Anette Holck Draborg et al., 2014), Draborg et al. 2016 (Anette Holck Draborg et al., 2016), Vista et al. 2017 (Vista et al., 2017), Chougule et al. 2018 (Chougule et al., 2018) provided self-contradictory data. Even if all but the study of Vista et al. 2017 (Vista et al., 2017) support the hypothesis without EBV infection no SLE the data of these studies were not considered for a re-analysis. The same studies provide evidence of a causal relationship k which is $k < 0$. This is a contradiction. Mathematically it is not possible to

obtain a significant condition sine qua non relationship, while the causal relationship $k < 0$. The data are potentially biased and were not considered (Table 3) for an analysis.

Table 3. Studies not considered for a re-analysis.

Study ID	Year	N	Case_P	Case_T	Con_P	Con_T	Odds Ratio	OR 95 % CI	OR upper	p(SINE)	X2 (SINE)	p Value (SINE)	K	IOU
Ngou et al.	1996	83	30	33	50	50	0,00	#ZAH!	#ZAH!	0,96386	0,2727272727	0,6015	-0,2384	0,3614
Zang et al.	1999	81	28	36	38	45	0,64	0,21	1,99	0,90123	1,7777777778	0,1824	-0,0853	0,2593
Huggins et al.	2005	61	26	36	22	25	0,35	0,09	1,45	0,83607	2,7777777778	0,0956	-0,1895	0,3770
Tazi et al.	2009	88	40	44	42	44	0,48	0,08	2,75	0,95455	0,3636363636	0,5465	-0,0902	0,4318
US et al.	2011	100	49	50	50	50	0,00	#ZAH!	#ZAH!	0,99000	0,0200000000	0,8875	-0,1005	0,4900
Essen et al.	2012	263	184	198	64	65	0,21	0,03	1,59	0,94677	0,9898989899	0,3198	-0,1029	0,6958
Broccolo et al.	2013	59	18	21	35	38	0,51	0,09	2,81	0,94915	0,4285714286	0,5127	-0,1012	0,2542
Draborg et al.	2014	44	19	22	21	22	0,30	0,03	3,15	0,93182	0,4090909091	0,5224	-0,1581	0,4091
Draborg et al.	2016	54	24	27	26	27	0,31	0,03	3,16	0,94444	0,3333333333	0,5637	-0,1414	0,4259
Chougule et al.	2017	137	76	87	46	50	0,60	0,18	2,00	0,91971	1,3908045977	0,2383	-0,0716	0,5255
Vista et al.	2017	997	202	233	685	764	0,75	0,48	1,17	0,96891	4,1244635193	0,0423	-0,0400	0,1234
Total		1967	696	787	1079	1180								

2.1.3. Studies considered for causal relationship re-analysis

The concept of causality and causal inference is characterized by an increasingly prominent place in the teaching and practice of human medicine, epidemiology and science as such. However, a single and generally accepted approach to causal inference in science is still not in sight. In particular, this publication analyzed the etiopathogenetic relationship between EBV and SLE (Table 4) while relying on antibodies against EBV. The EBV antibodies itself are not regarded as a or as the cause of SLE. Human antibodies against EBV represent a prototype of persistent EBV infection of humans characterized by the property of the latency and reactivation.

Table 4. Studies considered for a causal analysis

Study ID	Year	N	Case_P	Case_T	Con_P	Con_T	Odds Ratio	OR 95 % CI lower	OR upper	p(SINE)	X ² (SINE)	p Value (SINE)	k	p-value
Yokochi et al.	1989	25	9	11	2	14	27,00	3,17	229,97	0,92000	0,3636363636	0,5465	0,6753	0,0011228519
Marchini et al.	1994	60	34	40	15	20	1,89	0,50	7,17	0,90000	0,9000000000	0,3428	0,1218	0,1736510702
Tsai et al.	1995	36	13	16	15	20	1,44	0,29	7,25	0,91667	0,5625000000	0,4533	0,0747	0,2869181245
James et al.	1997	270	116	117	107	153	49,87	6,76	367,95	0,99630	0,0085470085	0,9263	0,3817	0,0000000000
Westgeest et al.	1998	98	10	14	56	84	1,25	0,36	4,34	0,95918	1,1428571429	0,2850	0,0355	0,2325337341
Kitagawa et al.	1998	131	64	65	52	66	17,23	2,19	135,40	0,99237	0,0153846154	0,9013	0,3089	0,0002635504
Lau et al.	1998	56	27	34	4	22	17,36	4,43	68,01	0,87500	1,4411764706	0,2299	0,6015	0,0000070593
Strata et al.	1999	115	55	60	33	55	7,33	2,53	21,22	0,95652	0,4166666667	0,5186	0,3732	0,0000490555
James et al.	2001	588	195	196	370	392	11,59	1,55	86,67	0,99830	0,0051020408	0,9431	0,1241	0,0008692782
Chen et al.	2005	72	31	36	30	36	1,24	0,34	4,50	0,93056	0,6944444444	0,4047	0,0386	0,2429624922
Parks et al.	2005	506	220	230	256	276	1,72	0,79	3,75	0,98024	0,4347826087	0,5097	0,0611	0,0598564420

Berkun et al.	2009	260	114	120	127	140	1,94	0,72	5,29	0,97692	0,3000000000	0,5839	0,0821	0,0816128126
Chen et al.	2010	464	81	94	308	370	1,25	0,66	2,39	0,97198	1,7978723404	0,1800	0,0320	0,1023368848
Draborg et al.	2012	80	48	60	15	20	1,33	0,40	4,40	0,85000	2,4000000000	0,1213	0,0529	0,2137718782
Csuka et al.	2012	646	286	301	310	345	2,15	1,15	4,03	0,97678	0,7475083056	0,3873	0,0964	0,0057414496
Han et al.	2018	192	104	116	68	76	1,02	0,40	2,62	0,93750	1,2413793103	0,2652	0,0029	0,1897224260
Total		3599	1407	1510	1768	2089								

Alpha = 0,05

Degrees of freedom = 16

χ^2 CRITICAL (k) = 26,296

χ^2 Calculated (k) = 124,72

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Data analysis

The causal relationship k (I. Baruk i , 2016, 2018c, 2018b, 2019b; K. Baruk i & Baruk i , 2016; K. Baruk i , Baruk i , & Baruk i , 2018) was used to proof the data for a causal relationship while the significance was tested by the hypergeometric distribution (HGD) and the chi-square distribution (Pearson, 1900). The *conditio sine qua non* (I. Baruk i , 2016, 2018c, 2018b, 2019b; K. Baruk i & Baruk i , 2016; K. Baruk i et al., 2018) relationship (SINE) was used to proof the hypothesis, *without EBV no SLE*. The index of unfairness (I. Baruk i , 2019a) was used to control publication bias. All statistical analyses were performed with Microsoft® Excel® for Mac® version 16.2 (181208) software (© 2018, Microsoft GmbH, Munich, Germany). The level of significance was set to 0.05.

Example.

Gaseous oxygen (A) is vital for human life (C). Under completely gaseous oxygen free conditions, no human being can survive for a longer time. How long can an average human being live without oxygen depends upon circumstances. However, without gaseous oxygen, no human life on our planet. Gaseous oxygen is a necessary condition of human life. In point of fact, without appropriate water (B) no human life (C) too, we can't survive without water (B). Thus far, even if gaseous oxygen is present, if there is no water, we will not survive. Human life can exist only in the presence of appropriate conditions. A risk factor A (i.e. gaseous oxygen), which is necessary condition of an outcome C needs not to be the only necessary condition of an outcome C. Another risk factor B (i. e. water) can be a necessary condition too. How many necessary conditions may determine the outcome C, without one single necessary condition no outcome C.

3. Results

THEOREM 1. WITHOUT EBV VCA IgG ANTIBODY POSITIVITY NO SLE

CLAIM.

Null-Hypothesis: EBV VCA IgG Antibody positivity is a necessary condition of SLE.

Alternative Hypothesis: EBV VCA IgG Antibody positivity is not a necessary condition of SLE.

PROOF.

Many times, it is difficult to test a hypothesis in all people of a population. Due to many reasons, there is a need to draw inferences about phenomena in the population from events observed in a sample. However, no matter how many data a researcher collects, a sample which is inadequate to represent the target population (IOU = +0,274) and an inappropriate sample size may have influence on research outcomes and can compromise the conclusions drawn from the data of a study. Moreover, the widespread belief that large samples are ideal for research is not always true. A large a sample may amplify the detection of differences and emphasizing statistical differences which are not justified. In contrast to a large study, a study with a smaller sample size may not be able to detect an existing difference between study groups. In this context, the central limit theorem is the cornerstone of modern statistics. According to the central limit theorem, if the sample size from the population is sufficiently large (rule of thumb: $n \geq 30$), then the mean of the sample is approximately normally distributed regardless of the population distribution. The publication bias of the studies considered for meta-analysis was more or less acceptable (Average IOU = +0,274). According to the data analyzed (**Table 2**) with a sample size of $N=3599$ it was not possible (Degrees of freedom =16; $X^2_{\text{Calculated}}(\text{SINE})= 12,47$; $X^2_{\text{CRITICAL}}(\text{SINE}) =26,296$) to reject the null-hypothesis, because $X^2_{\text{Calculated}}(\text{SINE}) < X^2_{\text{CRITICAL}}(\text{SINE})$. We reject the alternative hypothesis and accept the Null-hypothesis: *without* EBV VCA IgG antibody positivity *no* SLE. An EBV infection (detected by EBV VCA IgG) is a necessary condition of SLE.

QUOD ERAT DEMONSTRANDUM.

THEOREM 2. AN EBV INFECTION IS THE CAUSE OF SLE

CLAIM.

Null-Hypothesis: No causal relationship between EBV and SLE ($k = 0$).

Alternative Hypothesis: Causal relationship between EBV and SLE ($k \neq 0$).

PROOF.

The studies analyzed (**Table 4**) provided evidence of a significant causal relationship k ($n = 3599$; degrees of freedom =16; $X^2_{\text{Calculated}}(k) = 124,72$; $X^2_{\text{CRITICAL}}(k) = 26,296$). We reject the null-hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis because $X^2_{\text{Calculated}}(k) = 124,72 > X^2_{\text{CRITICAL}}(k) = 26,296$. There is a highly significant causal relationship k between EBV and SLE. The data re-analyzed support the hypothesis too that an EBV infection is a necessary condition (**Table 2**) of SLE. Based on the data analyzed, the conclusion is justified that an *EBV infection is the cause of SLE*.

QUOD ERAT DEMONSTRANDUM.

4. Discussion

The etiology of systemic lupus erythematosus is still not well understood. Various risk factors including ultraviolet radiation (Bijl & Kallenberg, 2006; Kirchof & Dutz, 2014; Kuhn & Beissert, 2005; Kuhn, Wenzel, & Weyd, 2014; Lehmann, Hölzle, Kind, Goerz, & Plewig, 1990; Meller et al., 2005), geographical distribution (Pan et al., 2014; Qian et al., 2014), seasonal distribution (Amit, Molad, Kiss, & Wysesbeek, 1997; Duarte-García, Fang, To, Magder, & Petri, 2012), climate factors (Chiche et al., 2012; Hua-Li, Shi-Chao, De-Shen, Dong, & Hua-Feng, 2011; Léone et al., 1997; Szeto et al., 2008; Yang et al., 2012) such as wind speed, atmospheric pressure, temperature, mean humidity, and precipitation and other (Pan et al., 2019) environmental risk factors (Deapen et al., 1992) are discussed to be involved in the pathogenesis of SLE. However, studies published provided very contradictory results. Various studies provided evidence that especially ultraviolet radiation (UVR) including UVA (wavelength range: 320-400 nm), UVB (wavelength range: 290-320 nm) and UVC (wavelength range: 200-290 nm), is one of the most important environmental risk factors (Bijl & Kallenberg, 2006; Kirchof & Dutz, 2014; Kuhn & Beissert, 2005; Kuhn et al., 2014; Lehmann et al., 1990; Meller et al., 2005) which is able to induce SLE. In point of fact, studies reported conflicting results on the relationship between UVR and SLE and the role of UVR in the development of SLE remains controversial. First of all, systemic lupus erythematosus is an autoimmune disease with diverse clinical presentation which involves multiple organ systems and not only those parts of human body, which are exposed very often and intensively to UVR (i.e. lupus nephritis). Furthermore, and in contrast to expectation, McGrath et al. (McGrath, Bak, & Michalski, 1987) demonstrated 1987 that low-dose UVR markedly prolonged lupus survival and decreased lupus mortality. Paradoxically, a low-dose, long-term UVA therapy was able to decrease clinical disease activity in SLE significantly (McGrath, 1994, 2005;

McGrath, Martínez-Osuna, & Lee, 1996; Molina & McGrath, 1997, 1997). Thus far, other risk factors than UVR are more likely to provide to the etiology of SLE. Especially EBV has been suspected to be related to SLE. Evans et al. (Evans et al., 1971) were one of the first who were able to report raised antibody titres to EBV in systemic lupus erythematosus patients. Epstein et al. detected (Epstein et al., 1964) the EBV virus in 1964 in cultured Burkitt lymphoma cells. Epstein Barr virus (EBV), is a gamma-herpesvirus which infects at least 90% of the population worldwide (J. I. Cohen, 2000) and is able to cause different clinical syndromes, including mononucleosis (Filatov, 1904; Godt, 2010; Hoagland, 1955; Sprunt & Evans, 1920) or Emil Pfeiffer's (1846–1921) disease (Godt, 2010), multiple sclerosis (I. Baruk i , 2018b; K. Baruk i & Baruk i , 2016), rheumatoid arthritis (K. Baruk i et al., 2018), Hodgkin's disease (I. Baruk i , 2018a) and possibly a number of other malignancies too. Most patients are exposed to EBV by early adulthood. After the primary infection, Epstein-Barr virus establishes latency by persistence for life in long-term memory B cells (Babcock, Decker, Volk, & Thorley-Lawson, 1998) in the peripheral blood of human host. Even if controlled (more or less) by host's immune system, EBV can reactivate later in life to produce different diseases. The severity and presentation of an acute infection with EBV can vary widely ranging from a life-threatening version of mononucleosis (liver damage, splenomegaly) to an asymptomatic infection. In this context, serological markers for EBV infection are often commonly used diagnostic tools for this purpose. However, an Epstein-Barr virus (EBV) infection is accompanied with the fact that IgG-antibodies to Epstein-Barr nuclear antigen 1 (EBNA-1) and IgM- and IgG-antibodies to viral capsid antigen (VCA) can occur simultaneously both during subclinical viral reactivation and in late primary infection (Nystad & Myrmel, 2007) and the interpretation of EBV serologies remains a challenge to some extent. Therefore, under such circumstances, it appears to be a little bit difficult to distinguish a primary EBV infection, a reactivation of latent infection or evidence of a past EBV infection only by means of EBV-specific serology. However, a task which is difficult is therefore not impossible (Linde & Falk, 2007). Klutts et al. (Klutts, Ford, Perez, & Gronowski, 2009) conducted a study with a large population of patients to develop techniques for interpreting multiplexed EBV results. The presence of EBV VCA IgG in the absence of EBV VCA IgM and EBV EBNA 1 IgG antibodies indicates a past infection with EBNA 1 IgG loss or non appearance but equally an acute EBV infection with the early disappearance or delayed onset of EBV VCA IgM (De Paschale et al., 2009). In the present study, EBV VCA IgG positivity was used as an indicator that an individual

investigated is EBV positive. However, EBV VCA IgG is catabolized in patients at a certain rate with half-life of circulating immunoglobulin G (IgG) of roughly 10–21 days (Mankarious et al., 1988) depending on IgG isotype and other factors. Due to this fact, false negative results in this study cannot be excluded.

The validity of any clinical research and thus far of this study too may be affected by chance, generalizability, and bias. There are many hidden biases which can negatively affect the outcome of a study, the sample size is only one of these factors. One should note, however, that the studies included in this meta-analysis have to some extent small sample sizes and laboratory practice is lacking a general standard. Even if EBV is able to generate multiple antibodies in the serum, EBV VCA IgG is generally considered as a sensitive indicator of an exposure to EBV. Since EBV persist for life in memory B cells (Babcock et al., 1998) EBV VCA IgG is used as evidence of EBV positivity. Meanwhile, a number of observations have been made linking EBV to SLE (Chêne et al., 2007; Daibata, Speck, Mulder, & Sairenji, 1994) but it remains uncertain whether there is a causal relationship between the virus and SLE. The reviews on the relationship between EBV and SLE are very rare. In toto, only two studies investigated this relationship. Hanlon et al. (Hanlon et al., 2014) included 25 studies in their meta-analysis of case–control studies while inappropriate studies were not excluded from analysis to a necessary extent. Still, Hanlon et al. (Hanlon et al., 2014) found a significant association between SLE and serological markers of an EBV VCA IgG (OR = 2.08, 95% CI 1.15 to 3.76). Li et al. (Li et al., 2019) meta-analysed 19 studies, including studies with self-contradictory data too, and found only a significant association between EBV sero-positivity and SLE (OR: 3.86, 95% CI 1.52–9.83, $p = 0.005$) based on VCA antibodies. Both reviews failed to provide evidence of a cause effect relationship between EBV and SLE. In this review, at the end 27 studies with a sample size of $n = 5566$ were identified for a review. The strengths of this meta-analysis includes the search strategy and the absence of self-contradictory data in the analysis. In toto, 11 studies with a sample size of $n = 1967$ provided self-contradictory data and were not considered for a meta-analysis even if all of these studies but the study of Vista et al. 2017 (Vista et al., 2017) supported the Null-hypothesis: *without* EBV infection *no* SLE (**Table 2**). However it is remarkable and necessary to make an effort to pay attention to the fact that the studies analyzed failed to provide evidence of a significant *conditio per quam* relationship between EBV and SLE which is highly logical and additionally supports the findings of this study. In summary, the evidence of the relationship between EBV and SLE is at the end probably stronger then suggested by

the results of this study. The analysis of the causal relationship between EBV and SLE is grounded on 16 studies with a sample size of $n = 3599$. The data of the studies analyzed support the alternative hypothesis that there is a cause effect relationship between EBV and SLE (**Table 4**). Taken together, since *without* an EBV infection *no* SLE occurs (**Table 2**), the conclusion is justified that EBV is the cause of SLE. This meta-analysis of case–control studies investigating the causal relationship between SLE and EBV VCA IgG as a serological marker of an EBV infection is, to our knowledge, the first study which provides clear significant evidence of a cause effect relationship between EBV and SLE. While this study focused on EBV VCA IgG indicator of an EBV infection, future studies are warranted and should investigate other markers of an EBV positivity to confirm or refute the findings of this study.

5. Conclusion

In summary, these findings support the hypothesis that *without* an EBV infection *no* SLE, while there is a significant cause effect relationship between EBV and SLE too. In conclusion, the findings of this review provide clear support for the hypothesis that *EBV is not only a cause but the cause of SLE*.

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